

REPORT

Agricultural Developmental Activities to Double the Crop Yield of Biso Block of Mayurbhanj District of Odisha During This Corona Period

Satyajit Marndi^{1*}, R.Subudhi^{1†} & C.R.Subudhi^{1‡*}

¹Department of SWCE, CAET, OUAT, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

[†]rsubudhi5906@gmail.com. [‡]Contributed equally.

Received : May 29, 2020; Accepted : June 06, 2020; Published : June 12, 2020.

Abstract

An experiment was conducted to find out the difficulties in increase the crop yield of Biso block of Mayurbhanj district of Odisha, during the year 2020 at OUAT, Bhubaneswar under U.G.course[1]. The Biso block of Mayurbhanj district is located in the North-East part of Odisha. Latitude - 22° 9' 31.7520" N; Longitude - 86° 24' 35.5392" E; Altitude – 112m. Mayurbhanj district is bounded by the Jharkhand State in the north, Balasore district in the south, West Bengal State in the east and Keonjhar district in the west. Mayurbhanj district covers a geographical area of 10418 sq.km which place in the 1st position in terms of geographical area in the state as per Census of India i.e. 6.69% of land of the total landmass of the state. As per 2011 census, the population of the district is 23.48 lakhs which ranks 3rd position in the state. The soil of the district may be broadly classified into Matured Red & Lateritic soil (Alfisols), Mixed Grey Soil (Inceptisols) and Unaltered Soils with coarse parent materials (Entosols). The red soil is further classified into three subgroups namely, Typical soil, Red loamy soil and Clay - loam soil. The geographical area of the block is 37,291 Ha and gross and net cropped area is 23,287 and 18,535 Ha respectively. So to improve the crop yield the farmers should go for a soil test, improved variety, required quantity of fertilizer as per soil test and soil conservation measures and use of Agril implements. A Marketing facility should be there along with banking facility, so that the farmers will not go to outside state for getting money.

Key words: Agricultural Developmental Activities Double Crop Yield Odisha Corona Virus.

Introduction

Mayurbhanj – a district in the northern Odisha historically famous as the "land of the maharajas", is also known for its dominant tribal population, vibrant culture, the famous Similipal forests, Chhau dance, beautiful temples, stone, dhokra and tassar work and of course "mudhi" among other things. The district gets its name from the continuous reign of two ancient kingdoms for over a thousand years – the "Mauryas" and the "Bhanjas" until its merger with the state of Odisha on January 1, 1949.

It is located in the North-East part of Odisha. The geographical extent of the district is 85°40" to 87°11" East longitudes and between 21°16" to 22°34" North latitudes falling in the series of survey of India toposheets no. s F45H, F45I, F45J, F45N, F45O AND F45P (Open Series map)

It is bounded by the Jharkhand State in the north, Balasore district in the south, West Bengal State in the east and Keonjhar district in the

west. Mayurbhanj district covers a geographical area of 10418 sq.km which place in the 1st position in terms of geographical area in the state as per Census of India i.e. 6.69% of land of the total landmass of the state. As per 2011 census, the population of the district is 23.48 lakhs which ranks 3rd position in the state. (Maranndi & Subudhi 2020)

Result and Discussion

District Profile

The Mayurbhanj district is divided into 4 administrative sub-divisions. The sub-divisions are as follow:

- Baripada
- Bamanghati with headquarter at Rairangpur.
- Panchpir with headquarter at Karanjia
- Kaptipada with headquarter at Udala.

Apart from the sub-divisions, the district consists of 26 tahasils, 26 blocks, 382 Gram Panchayats, 1 Municipality, 3 Notified Area Councils (NAC), and 32 Police stations. Figure 1 shows the administrative map of Mayurbhanj district. Let's assume I'm the Assistant Agricultural Officer in Bamanghati Sub Division, Bisoi Block

Bisoi Block

Latitude - 22° 9' 31.7520" N; Longitude - 86° 24' 35.5392" E; Altitude - 112m. Mayurbhanj district (Figure 1) has 26.83 lakhs of population, which male population is 1168880, female population is 1179582 and children population is 334946 (2011 census). The geographical area of the district is 10418 sq.km. As per 2011 Census, the total Schedule Caste (SC) population is 165493 whereas the Schedule Tribes (ST) population is 1448193. The information shows that the district is highly distributed with ST population. The total households in the district is 547769.

Figure 1. Mayurbhanj District For Bisoi Block Specifically

Soil Profile

The soil of the district may be broadly classified into Matured Red & Lateritic soil (Alfisols), Mixed Grey Soil (Inceptisols) and Unaltered Soils with coarse parent materials (Entosols). The red soil is further classified into three subgroups namely, Typical soil, Red loamy soil and Clay-loam soil. Typical red soil is found mostly in the hills of Bamanghati & Panchpir sub-divisions and is suitable mainly for paddy, millets, sabai grass and other minor crops. The Red loamy soil, which is found near river banks, is suitable for early variety paddy, groundnut, tile, castor, black mung and kulthi. The clay-loam type is found in the sub-divisions of Kaptipada & Baripada. Medium & late varieties of paddy are grown on this soil

Soil Erosion & Run off Status

Soil erosion occurs when soil is removed through the action of wind and water at a great rate than it is formed. Concentrated high rainfall in monsoon period with sufficient surface gradient and uncovered crop fields are observed to be the major causes of land degradation in the area. As porous soil, they have the poor moisture retention capacity and are subject to heavy runoff soil erosion. The geographical area of the block is 37,291 Ha and gross and net cropped area is 23,287 and 18,535 Ha respectively. Slight of Bisoi is 20856.3 Ha. (Table 1)

Weakness & Threats to Agricultural Practices (SWOT Analysis)

Weakness

- The farms are totally rain-fed.
- No fencing and shortage of farm implements.
- Communication facility is poor.
- Few available homesteads land.
- Regular vacancies in technical and administrative staffs.
- More than half of the farmers are tribal and illiterate.
- Regional Research & Technology Transfer Station are far away.

Threats

- Occurrence of droughts.
- Grazing of animal & threat problem.
- Non availability of transport during off hours.
- Naxalite problem.
- Backstopping of technology isn't quickly available.

How can we double the crop yield of the farmers residing in the Bisoiblock ?

Plant Early, Plant Effectively

Choosing the right time to plant is often the most important part of planting. The best strategy to use to increase yields is: if your soil is ready, start planting. There are tests you can perform on your soil to see if it is ready for planting. Today's hybrid seeds create a more sustainable product, but knowing if your field is ready for early planting is just as important. Planting early can result in increased yields by taking advantage of unexpectedly early favourable soil conditions.

Practice Seasonal Soil Rotation

When you are planting season-by-season, it is important to understand how planting recurring crops can affect your overall yield. Planting corn in consecutive years has been proven to be less effective for optimal yields. This means that corn-on-corn, planting should only be considered when your soil conditions are strong enough, or your land mass is limited. If you don't have access to either, you may need to consider planting alternative crops in alternating years – such as soybeans. Planting an alternating crop helps to diversify the demands on your soil. This results in crops that not only yield more, but continually produce year in and year out.

Know The Yield Potential

It is not just enough to plan your seeds and hope for the best, you should always be sure to understand your field's growth potential. Understanding the kind of crops, you're planting, and the kinds of seeds you are using, is important when assessing yield potential. Crop producers typically have an estimated idea of the yield potential of their seeds. Understanding this will help manage not only your expectations, but whether or not your yield potential is matching your actual production.

Always Scout Your Fields

The sagest advice you can receive about how to increase crop yields is by scouting your fields on foot. This will give you a chance to assess soil conditions, notice any weeds cropping up, and check that your crops are growing healthily. There is a lot you can miss when you are passing by your crops at high speeds, so hitting the ground and examining your crops is an important step towards a stronger crop yield.

Ensure Proper Water Drainage

Water management is essential to crop survival and maximizing your corn's yield potential. It's important to ensure your crop is getting enough water, but also that they aren't being over-watered.

Table 1. Land Use Pattern

Sl.no	Name of the block	Geographical Area	Area Under Agriculture						
			Gross crop other uses per area	Net area sown	Area sown more than once	Cropping intensity	Area under forest	Area under waste land	Area under other uses
1	Bisoi	37291	23287	18535	4752	125.638	7248	107	165

Developing a drainage system in your crops can help prevent water-logging and salinization in your soil, both of which can stifle growth and production.

Utilize Fertilizers

Cultivating your soil with fertilizers is an important part of maintaining optimal soil conditions for crops on your farmland. Fertilizing your corn at the time of seeding can help provide the seeds with essential nutrients like potassium, phosphorous, and calcium. The root-zone at the base of your crops is the most important area to facilitate growth so your corn can thrive and produce an impressive yield.

Test Your Soil

Soil testing should be on your to do list right from the get-go, because your soil and its needs will directly influence the growth of your crops. Examining the phosphorus, potassium, and fertilization levels will give you insight into how to handle your crops. It will also let you know when proper soil conditions are forming, such as the optimal density and right amount of nutrients, so you are ready to start planting.

Weed Early and Often

Weeds are not just the enemy of front lawns and golf courses; they can also compromise your farmland. Weeds are invasive, and siphon nutrients away from the crops you are trying to grow. Weeds always need to be dealt with as early and often as possible. Scouting your fields gives you the opportunity to see if any weeds are cropping up – and putting a stop to them before the problem can get out of hand.

Seed Quality

Having quality seeds is the basis for increasing crop yields. Whether you are looking into increasing your corn yields, or maximizing your overall agricultural productivity, you need to consider the strength of your seeds. Using hybrid seeds that are naturally inclined to grow faster, stronger, and with greater efficiency is pivotal to the success of your crops. Non-GMO seeds combine sustainability and cost seamlessly, which accounts for both quality and cost

Conclusion

So to improve the crop yield the farmers should go for a soil test, improved variety, required quantity of fertilizer as per soil test and soil conservation measures and use of Agril implements. A Marketing facility should be there along with banking facility, so that the farmers will not go to outside state for getting money during this Corona virus period.

References

1. Marandi, S. and Subudhi, C. (2020). Report submitted for partial fulfillment of B.Sc Ag (Hon) degree.